

WAS MLK A VICTIM OF GOVERNMENT ENGINEERED ASSASSINATION?

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Martin Luther King a Nobel Peace Prize winner was assassinated In Memphis, TN. on April 4th, 1968. James Earl Ray was convicted of MLK's murder and later died in prison. In the last several decades, new information revealed that a conspiracy involving the FBI, the Memphis police and various governmental agencies participated in the assassination of MLK and a Memphis policeman was the actual killer. **Objective:** To answer, "Was MLK a victim of government engineered assassination?" **Method:** Application of the probability theory to project odds of certainty that MLK was a victim of a government sanctioned homicide. **Results:** 17 Observations consistent with "Frank Strausser Killed" and inconsistent with "MLK was not Killed by Frank Strausser" indicate MLK was a victim of a government sanctioned homicide. Odds of this observation being correct is% 99.999. **Discussion:** MLK's death was marked by "government sanctioned assassination".

- A. Death of a man of influence by a conspiracy.
- B. A discrepancy between official narrative of death and scientific evidence.
- C. A top secret national security reason for murder.
- D. Criminals never faced justice.
- E. Proven investigative failures by governmental agencies to solve a major crime of profound national and international importance.

Conclusion: Frank Strausser assassinated MLK with substantial help from the FBI, the Memphis police and various governmental agencies and James Earl Ray was wrongfully convicted of a murder he did not commit.

INTRODUCTION

Martin Luther King a civil rights leader who dreamt that all inhabitants of the United States would be judged by their personal qualities and not by the color of their skin received a Nobel Peace Prize for his nonviolent campaign against racism was assassinated in 1968.^[1,2,3,4]

MLK was fatally shot at 6:01 p.m., April 4, 1968, as he stood on the Lorraine motel's second-floor balcony in Memphis.^[1,2,3,4]

James Earl Ray was convicted of MLK's murder and later died in prison. In the last several decades new information revealed that James Earl Ray was set up as a fall guy by a conspiracy involving the FBI, the Memphis Police and various governmental agencies.^[1,2,3,4] On December 8th, 1999, the Memphis jury took less than an hour to find in favor of the King family to find Lloyd

Jowers and various governmental agencies guilty of MLK's assassination.^[1,2,3,4]

OBJECTIVE

Was MLK a victim of "government engineered assassination"?

METHOD

Application of the probability theory to project odds of certainty that MLK was a victim of a government sanctioned homicide. We conducted a literature search for Martin Luther King's assassination Identified 14 publications (1-14) as Informative and retrieved observations with either consistent or inconsistent with the observation that MLK was a victim of "government sanctioned homicide".

RESULTS

18 Observations consistent with MLK was a victim of a government sanctioned homicide and inconsistent with that he was not suggesting that MLK was killed by a government sanctioned conspiracy. Odds of this observation being correct is% 99.999

1. James Earl Ray the convicted killer of MLK was declared innocent by a civil jury verdict based upon new evidence.^[1,3,4]
2. A civil jury declared Loyd Jower guilty of conspiracy in the murder of MLK.^[1,3,4]
3. Loyd Jowers testifying by deposition stated that a Memphis police officer was the assassin of MLK.^[1,3,4]
4. Loyd Jowers' Death bed confession :” Frank Strauser killed MLK”.^[1]
5. Lenny B. Curtis deposition 2003: Frank Strauser killed MLK.^[1,3,4]
6. Witness report; Frank Strauser drove away in a red convertible after an intense shooting practice from 9am to 3pm on the day of MLK’s assassination.^[1,2]
7. Frank Strauser: “Why would I be in trouble for something I did 30 years ago?”^[1,2]
8. Frank Strauser “I only did what any good cop would have done”.^[1,2]
9. Frank Strauser:” King was a shit starter”.^[1,2]
10. Frank Strauser; “I was at home when I heard the news at 6 pm”, later, he claimed He heard the news while driving.^[1,2]
11. Frank Strauser: A decorated Vietnam veteran sharp shooter worked for MPD.
12. Frank Strauser did not protest or deny he was the shooter after he was informed by William Pepper of Loyd Jowers confession.^[1,2]
13. Frank Strauser agreed to collaborate with Pepper for a MLK book project.^[1,2]
14. Buddy Butler a key witness of MLK murder was killed.^[1,2]
15. Buddy Butler’s death: no police investigation or report of interview, no death notice.^[1,2]
16. Presence of a large military at Saint Joseph Hospital where MLK died.^[1,2]
17. Dr Breen Brand, surgeon at Joseph Hospital.: Let's stop working on that nagger. Let him die.^[1,2]
18. At the Lorraine hotel Dr Kings room was switched from one of a secluded ground floor courtyard to a highly exposed one with a balcony.^[1,2]

DISCUSSION

Forensic and mathematical evidence suggests Frank Strauser assassinated MLK with substantial help from the FBI, the Memphis police and various governmental agencies and James Earl Ray was wrongfully convicted of a murder he did not commit.

MLK's tragic death is marked by signature traits of “government engineered assassination”

- A. Death of a man of influence by a conspiracy.
- B. A discrepancy between official narrative of death and scientific evidence.
Frank Strauser and not James Earl Ray Silenced MLK.
- C. A top secret national security reason for murder.
The most likely cause of MLK's murder was MLK's vigorous opposition to the Vietnam War and bombing civilians.
- D. Criminals never faced justice.
- E. Proven investigative failures by governmental agencies to solve a major crime.

Buddy Butler a key witness of MLK murder was killed: no police investigation or report of interview, no death notice.

Worthy of emphasis Is the striking similarities between the silencing of John F Kennedy and MLK marked by signature traits of a government sanctioned Assassination. David Mantik PhD, MD., an extraordinary JFK assassination researcher who proved that surgery was performed on JFK's brain at the Bethesda Naval Hospital suggested that JFK was killed by consensus. We may sadly observe that MLK’s death was also by consensus of diverse governmental agencies.

Of Importance, thanks to the extraordinary contributions of countless researchers and the introduction of a novel forensic method $R=1/2^x$ we can differentiate government engineered assassinations from random murders to combat GEA, a not easily observable foe of democracy.it is true that much progress has been recorded since 1968 yet GEA remains a dormant menace to democracy and further research is warranted.

Table A.

JFK &MLK Assassinations	JFK	MLK
1. Opposed to Vietnam War	+	+
2. Coordinated actions by Armed forces/intelligence agencies Insider help/killer assets	+	+
3. Insider/Informer help	Bundy	Jesse Jackson
4. Insiders upgraded after ass.	Bundy	Jesse Jackson
5. Change of assassination venue	Dealey Pl	Room with a balcony
6. Proven innocent patsies	Oswald	Ray
7. Grossly flawed investigation	Altered Autopsy	No Invest. of Buddy death
8. Coverup murders	Oswald, Ruby	Buddy

9. Medical Collusion	Altered autopsy	“ let nigger die “
	Dr Breen Brand	Saint Joseph hospital
10. Silenced officials after acknowledging responsibility for assassinations	William Colby/CIA	Willam Sullivan /FBI

CONCLUSION

Frank Strausser assassinated MLK with substantial help from the FBI, the Memphis police and various governmental agencies.

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